

Characterization of DAC Phase Offset in IEC 61850-9-2 Calibration Systems

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Abstract—This article presents an accurate and robust method to calculate the phase offset of a reference waveform, usually produced by a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) in IEC Std 61850-9-2 calibration systems. The phase offset is defined with respect to the rising edge of a reference clock signal, locked to the Global Positioning System (GPS). The proposed method relies on the synchronous acquisition of the DAC output and the clock signal. In the complex plane, where the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is defined, the acquired signals are processed to compensate the nonideal sampling rate and windowing. The method performance and its dependence from noise and parameters are thoroughly characterized by means of extensive numerical simulations. Two validation approaches, experimental and software-based, confirm the proposed method as a valuable and robust solution for calibration purposes.

Index Terms—Digital-to-analog converter (DAC) phase offset, discrete Fourier transform (DFT) interpolation, IEC 61850, phase reference signal (PRS), sampled values (SVs).

I. INTRODUCTION

IN MODERN power systems, the ever-increasing integration of renewable energy sources and distributed generation is pushing for the development of enhanced measurement techniques capable of coping with faster dynamics and higher distortion rates [1]–[3]. In this context, a new generation of instruments, such as phasor measurement units (PMUs) or stand-alone merging units (SAMUs), allows for monitoring the power system state by means of synchronized measurements, whose timestamp is referred to a common time reference. [4]–[6]. As a consequence, the role of National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) consists in providing calibration systems characterized by accuracy and stability levels significantly higher than the devices under test (DUTs) [7], [8].

In most PMU and SAMU calibrators [9]–[12], the test signal is synthesized by a digital-to-analog converter (DAC), supplied to the DUT and synchronously reacquired by an analog-to-digital converter (ADC). Then, the reacquired waveform is processed to extract the reference values to be compared with the DUT measurements [7].

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The rigorous characterization of the possible sources of uncertainty is a crucial task to guarantee the stability and reliability of the calibration system. In particular, the recent literature has focused on the phase offset contributions introduced by the generation and reacquisition stages. These phase offsets depend on the specific hardware architecture, namely, on the analog front-end circuitry and the ADC and DAC boards, as well as on the stability of the internal time-base. In this sense, the technical documentation might provide some interesting details, but the accuracy of such information is typically insufficient for calibration purposes. As a consequence, NMIs have developed *ad hoc* techniques for the precise and accurate assessment of phase offsets associated with the different components of the measurement chain.

At National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), the phase offset in the PMU calibrator is assessed by measuring on the oscilloscope the time shift of the test signal zero-crossing with respect to the pulse-per-second (PPS) signal of a Global Positioning System (GPS) clock [13]. At the Dutch Metrology Institute (VSL), the test signal is acquired by an ADC triggered by a PPS signal aligned to Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), and then analyzed via fast Fourier transform to extract the initial phase of the fundamental component [14]. A further enhancement is proposed by the joint collaboration of the Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology (METAS) and École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) [8]. Triggered by the PPS, the ADC acquires both the test signal and a phase reference signal (PRS), directly derived by the internal time-base and locked to the PPS itself. To limit the leakage contributions, an interpolated discrete Fourier transform (DFT) algorithm extracts the initial phase associated with the fundamental component of each signal [16]. The difference between test and clock signal phase accounts for the DAC time delay only. At the Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRiM), a similar approach is carried out, but in the time domain. In this way, the analysis does not suffer from the approximation of continuous spectrum signals in the DFT domain [17]. In more detail, the time shift between the test signal and the PRS is assessed by means of an high-accuracy phase comparator [18]. Finally, a recent collaboration between NIST and METAS has proposed a further modification. The low-pass filtering effects on both test and PRS signals due to the analog front-end of ADC and DAC are taken into account by means of a nonlinear fit routine with a customized logistic function model [19]. Such sophisticated techniques provide an estimation accuracy in the order of few tens of microradians at

the rated system frequency (i.e., 50 or 60 Hz), at the expense of significant time-consuming and computationally expensive procedures.

In this article, we consider a calibration system for measurement devices whose communication protocol relies on the IEC Std 61850-9-2 [20], in the following referred to as IEC Std for the sake of brevity. Such a calibration system basically compares an analog reference signal with its digitized version, which is encoded in the so-called sampled values (SVs) and then delivered through the network according to the previous introduced communication protocol. Depending on the DUT type, the SV can be converted by the DUT from the analog reference signal or directly transmitted by the calibration system itself. In both cases, however, it is of outstanding importance to generate synchronized signals and, in particular, to accurately know the initial phase with which these signals are generated. In this context, the compliance verification requires to supply the DUT with a test signal timestamped to the reference timing source with a phase uncertainty lower than 1 mrad [21]. At the rated system frequency, such uncertainty corresponds to a time delay of 3.18 and 2.65 μs for 50 and 60 Hz, respectively. In this sense, the accuracy requirements are slightly relaxed if compared with the aforementioned PMU calibrator accuracy levels. Nevertheless, recent literature has proposed several methods to effectively determine the DAC time delay with simplified approaches that could be run online or in quasi real-time conditions [11], [12], [22].

Article Contributions

We present a novel method for determining the DAC phase offset that guarantees high accuracy and reduced computational complexity. The method relies on the combined analysis of the test signal and the PRS. The generation and reacquisition stages share the same time-base (for the sampling rate definition) and time reference (for the trigger definition). This guarantees a nearly ideal synchronization between the two processes. The acquired waveforms are processed in the complex plane where the DFT is defined: an interpolation technique allows for minimizing the spectral leakage effects due to nonideal operating conditions (e.g., nonperfectly uniform sampling rate, or data window containing a noninteger number of fundamental cycles). The method performance is assessed by means of numerical simulations that evaluate the main influence quantities. As further proof, the method results are validated against two reference methods, relying on a fast current comparator and on a nonlinear fit [19]. The presented results and their consistency with the other methods prove the reliability of the proposed method, which provides the further advantage of a reduced computational complexity and an easy integration within the considered calibration system. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the only method capable of determining the phase offset of the DAC output with respect to the synchronization reference signal in a single step and characterized by a measurement uncertainty compatible with calibration requirements.

This article is structured as follows. Section II describes the measurement setup and the main technical features and

Fig. 1. (a) Block diagram of the measurement setup. The dashed rectangle contains the rectifier and oscilloscope used for experimental validation. (b) Flowchart showing the steps of synchronized generation and acquisition of the signals.

operating requirements involved in the calibration procedure. Section III presents the novel method for accurate determination of DAC delay and evaluates its performance dependence from main influence quantities. Finally, the method results are validated against two reference approaches in Section IV.

II. MEASUREMENT SETUP

As shown in Fig. 1, the measurement setup consists of the same hardware architecture as the IEC Std calibration system, originally proposed in [12]. In more detail, the NI PXI 1031 chassis (National Instruments, Austin, TX, USA) hosts two boards.

- 1) The NI PXI 6683 timing and synchronization module.
- 2) The NI PXI 4461 dynamic signal acquisition module.

The first one guarantees proper alignment of the internal time-base with respect to GPS and manages the synchronization between different acquisition and generation tasks by means of dedicated trigger signals. To this end, the NI PXI 6683 is disciplined by a Meinberg LANTIME M600 Time Server (Meinberg Funkhuren, Bad Pyrmont, Germany) that includes a GPS reference clock, whose time accuracy and frequency stability are in the order of 50 ns and 0.5 nHz/Hz over an average time of 1800 s, respectively, [12]. The internal time-base has a frequency of 10 MHz and allows for defining targeted triggers (as future time events) with a resolution of 10 ns and a latency not larger than 2 ns. These triggers are implemented as transistor-transistor logic (TTL) signals whose parameters are defined as follows: the amplitude is equal to 3.3 V, the frequency is set by the user as an integer divider of the 10-MHz time-base, and the initial phase accounts for the delay with respect to the PPS occurrence. The initial phase is configurable as an integer multiple of the time-base resolution. On its front panel, the NI PXI 6683 allows for making these triggers available as PRS at the programmable function interface (PFI) terminals.

The second module consists of two couples of 24-bit ADC and DAC channels, with input and dynamic range equal to ± 10 V and 90 dB, respectively. The sampling rate is derived from a 10-MHz temperature compensated quartz oscillator, ranging from 1 to 204.8 kSa/s with a resolution of $181.9 \mu\text{Sa/s}$. In the considered calibration system, the chosen sampling rates have discrepancies from the nominal values of a maximum of 1 ppb. The synchronization module can either trigger each channel separately or operate them simultaneously. The linearity of the digitizer has also been characterized and can be properly compensated with an uncertainty of $1 \mu\text{V/V}$ in the frequency range of interest, namely, from dc to few kilohertz [23].

As shown in the flowchart in Fig. 1(b), the analog output channel ao0 reproduces a sinusoidal waveform reference signal (WRS), whose amplitude, frequency, and initial phase are selected according the IEC Std requirements. The WRS is simultaneously reacquired by the analog input channel ai1. The PRS that triggers ao0 and ai1 is also acquired by ai0. In this way, the measurement setup gets a synchronous acquisition of both WRS and PRS, which can be further processed to determine the respective phase offset introduced by generation and acquisition stages (see Section III). Both PRS and WRS are generated and reacquired with 50- Ω coaxial cables of the same length, and therefore, the delay due to the signal propagation through the wire is the same and is automatically eliminated in the postprocessing calculation. The contribution of the electromagnetic properties, such as parasitic inductance and capacitance, can be considered negligible since their effect is not visible above the noise level.

In this article, all measurements were performed in a laboratory with a controlled room temperature of $(23 \pm 0.5)^\circ\text{C}$. Nevertheless, the proposed method presented can be customized, without loss of generality, to similar measurement setups equipped with synchronous generation and reacquisition modules.

In Fig. 1(a), the dashed rectangle contains a possible experimental setup for the validation of the proposed method. As further discussed in Section IV, a high-resolution oscilloscope is used to visualize PPS, PRS, and WRS as rectified by a fast current comparator. The PPS provides the trigger and accounts for the traceability to the common time reference, whereas the comparison between the rising edges of PRS and WRS is used to infer the DAC phase offset.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

In this section, the proposed method for the estimation of the DAC phase offset ϕ_{DAC} with respect to a traceable time reference (namely, the PPS rising edge) is presented. In the following, we describe the measurement procedure and the calculation steps. Finally, an evaluation of the main error and uncertainty sources is discussed.

A. Measurement Procedure

Given the measurement setup in Section II, the WRS and the PRS are simultaneously reacquired with cables of same length and recorded. For this analysis, the PRS is locked to

the PPS rising edge, with a jitter lower than 1 ns, as measured on the oscilloscope. It is thus reasonable to assume that the acquisition process begins in correspondence of a PPS rising edge. However, the timestamp associated with the record first sample does not coincide with the PPS occurrence, but presents a delay that can be ascribed to two main contributions.

- 1) The trigger latency introduced by the synchronization module and the digitizer clock delay (that is unknown and not measurable in the present setup).
- 2) The low-pass filtering effect inherent in the DAC and ADC analog front-ends.

For the sake of simplicity, in the following, the time delay introduced by the DAC and ADC is referred to as t_{DAC} and t_{ADC} , whereas the contribution of the trigger latency is compensated by means of an *ad hoc* zero-crossing detection method. Its residual contribution is expected to be orders of magnitude lower than DAC and ADC contributions, and thus negligible for the considered application scenario. In this regard, the specification of the acquisition model might provide useful insights into the filtering effects due to DAC and ADC analog front-ends. However, the accuracy of such technical specifications is typically insufficient for calibration purposes. For instance, in the present case, the NI PXI 4461 datasheet defines t_{DAC} and t_{ADC} in terms of integer number of samples (depending on the adopted sampling rate). This limits the resolution of the delay estimation to a sampling period: assuming a sampling rate of 150 kSa/s; the delay is known up to $6.67 \mu\text{s}$, corresponding to circa 2 mrad at 50 Hz, thus incompatible with the requirements of an IEC Std calibration system. For this reason, the present article proposes a measurement procedure and a computation method to improve the delay estimation accuracy.

As a preliminary test, we investigated the possible presence of interchannel delay. To this end, we alternatively swapped the channels for WRS generation and reacquisition. For this analysis, the WRS frequency and amplitude were set equal to 50 Hz and 10 V, respectively. Both DAC and ADC operated at a sampling rate of 204.8 kSa/s and the observation interval was equal to 4 s. We computed the DFT of the recorded signals and compared the initial phase associated with the fundamental component, identified as the DFT peak.¹ Given a phase discrepancy of few hundreds nrad, the combination of DAC and ADC contributions proves to be channel-independent.

Based on the adopted measurement setup, the PRS phase offset depends on the ADC contribution only, whereas that of the WRS accounts for both DAC and ADC. Therefore, an accurate estimation of the phase difference between WRS and PRS allows to determine ϕ_{DAC} . As mentioned, the PRS frequency f_{PRS} can only be a divider of the 10-MHz time-base. Therefore, to precisely compute the phase difference between PRS and WRS, the WRS frequency f_{WRS} should also be chosen such that

$$f_{\text{WRS}} = m \cdot f_{\text{PRS}}, \quad m \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

¹In the considered calibration scenario, it is reasonable to assume that the signals are acquired in the (quasi-)synchronous mode, and that aliasing and leakage effects can be minimized by properly defining the DFT window in terms of window length and possible weigh function, e.g., Hanning or Kaiser.

Fig. 2. Top plot: simulated PRS (solid line) and WRS with $m = 1$ (star symbols) and $m = 4$ (cross symbols) versus sample number after the PPS transition (dashed line). Bottom plot: ϕ_{DAC} computed starting the DFT window on the correspondent sample. Shaded areas represent the correct sample interval to start the DFT window.

where m determines the synchronization between WRS and PRS. If $m = 1$, the two signals are perfectly locked and the phase difference can be easily inferred from a DFT computed over an integer number of cycles. If $m \neq 1$, the first record sample becomes critical for the accurate definition of ϕ_{DAC} . Fig. 2 presents the relationship between a PRS and two simulated WRS with the same initial phase,² namely, $\hat{\phi}_{DAC} = -\pi/7$. One of the two WRSs has the same frequency as the PRS ($m = 1$), whereas the other one has a multiplication factor $m = 4$. In the first case, the initial sample of the DFT window is irrelevant, as the resulting ϕ_{DAC} coincides with the actual value. In the latter case, instead, the estimated ϕ_{DAC} depends on the location of the DFT window. In particular, the initial sample of the DFT window shall lie into an interval correspondent to one WRS cycle in the proximity of a PRS rising edge. The actual location of the most suitable sample interval is a function of ϕ_{DAC} and thus unknown *a priori*. Nevertheless, if the multiplication factor m is integer, the suitable interval recurs periodically at each rising edge of the PRS. Otherwise, this interval occurs with a periodicity p , which corresponds to the ratio between the PRS frequency and the greatest common divisor (gcd) of f_{prs} and f_{wrs}

$$p = \frac{f_{prs}}{\gcd(f_{prs}, f_{wrs})}. \quad (2)$$

In some cases, the combination between trigger latency and peculiar m values may push the first record sample outside this optimal interval and thus affect the estimation of ϕ_{DAC} . To prevent that, the initial sample of the DFT window shall be shifted to the next PRS rising edge, after a minimum number of samples n from the beginning of the signal record. In this regard, it is worth noticing that n has to be suitably defined such that the DFT window corresponds to the first PRS

²In the following, the hat symbol $\hat{\cdot}$ indicates any waveform parameter or quantity that is set by the user and thus perfectly known *a priori*.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the calculation method execution.

rising edge after the PPS occurrence, to correctly preserve the initial phase angle information. While for integer m values the PRS rising edge taken as reference is indifferent, in the case of noninteger rational m values instead, one has to be able to exactly identify the first PRS rising edge after the PPS. At a software level running on a non-real-time OS, this constraint can be fulfilled only by setting a series of future time event triggers related to the synchronized timing board and independent on the code flowing steps.

B. Calculation Method

The flowchart illustrated in Fig. 3 summarizes schematically the main steps of the proposed calculation method. Mathematical details are discussed extensively in the following.

Let N_{tot} be the total number of recorded samples on both acquisition channels, corresponding to an integer number of cycles of f_{prs} and f_{wrs} . The number of samples included in the DFT window N_{dft} depends on the location of the PRS rising edge and the corresponding shift by N_{shift} samples

$$N_{dft} = N_{tot} - N_{shift} - S_{sig} \quad (3)$$

where S_{sig} is the number of samples to be discarded to maintain an integer number of cycles for both signals

$$S_{sig} = \frac{f_s}{f_{sig}} - \text{mod}\left(N_{shift}, \frac{f_s}{f_{sig}}\right). \quad (4)$$

In the following, the sampling rate is denoted as f_s , whereas f_{sig} indicates the signal frequency, either PRS or WRS. In case these two frequencies are not equal $S_{prs} \neq S_{wrs}$ and, consequently, the DFTs are performed using two windows of a different length N_{dft} . Since both PRS and WRS are affected by the same ADC delay, and only the WRS initial phase accounts for the DAC contribution, the estimation of ϕ_{DAC} is based on the phases computed with the DFT, ϕ_{prs} and ϕ_{wrs}

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{prs} &= \phi_{ADC,prs} \\ \phi_{wrs} &= \phi_{DAC} + \phi_{ADC,wrs} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

whose difference yields

$$D_\phi = \phi_{wrs} - \phi_{prs} = \underbrace{(\phi_{ADC,wrs} - \phi_{ADC,prs})}_{\Delta\phi_{ADC}} + \phi_{DAC}. \quad (6)$$

The discrepancy between the ADC phase as measured on WRS and PRS $\Delta\phi_{ADC}$ depends on the noncoincident signal frequencies. To compensate this nonideal effect, the phases' ratio and difference can be suitably defined as

$$\begin{aligned} R_\phi &= \frac{\phi_{wrs}}{\phi_{prs}} = \frac{f_{wrs}t_{wrs}}{f_{prs}t_{ADC}}, \quad t_{ADC} \neq 0 \\ D_\phi &= \phi_{wrs} - \phi_{prs} = 2\pi \cdot (f_{wrs}t_{wrs} - f_{prs}t_{ADC}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $t_{\text{wrs}} = (t_{\text{DAC}} + t_{\text{ADC}})$. Such relationships can be gathered into a system of linear equations in terms of t_{DAC}

$$\begin{cases} t_{\text{DAC}} = t_{\text{ADC}} \cdot \left(\frac{f_{\text{prs}}}{f_{\text{wrs}}} R_{\phi} - 1 \right) \\ t_{\text{DAC}} = \frac{2\pi t_{\text{ADC}} \cdot (f_{\text{prs}} - f_{\text{wrs}}) + D_{\phi}}{2\pi f_{\text{wrs}}} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Then, $\Delta\phi_{\text{ADC}}$ is obtained by subtraction as

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{ADC}} = \frac{D_{\phi}}{1 - R_{\phi}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{f_{\text{wrs}}}{f_{\text{prs}}} \right). \quad (9)$$

Finally, by substituting (9) into (6), ϕ_{DAC} is defined as a function of the computed DFT phases

$$\phi_{\text{DAC}} = D_{\phi} - \frac{D_{\phi}}{1 - R_{\phi}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{f_{\text{wrs}}}{f_{\text{prs}}} \right). \quad (10)$$

In the complex plane where the DFT is computed, the signal frequency is defined over a discrete set of points, whose resolution depends on N_{dft} . In case of nonperfectly synchronous sampling, the DFT representation does not consist of a single significant coefficient but is affected by the so-called spectral leakage. In particular, we can identify a short-range spectral leakage (also known as picket fence) due to the imperfect alignment between the signal FT and the DFT axis, and a long-range spectral leakage due to the interference caused by the decaying lobes of the negative image component [24].

To minimize both these possible uncertainty sources, in this article, the initial phase ϕ_0 and the frequency f_0 associated with the signal fundamental component are extracted by means of an enhanced interpolated DFT (eIpDFT) [16]. The eIpDFT has been designed to overcome the DFT axis finite resolution and, at the same time, compensate the long-range leakage interference due to the negative image component

$$\text{eIpDFT} \rightarrow (\phi_0, f_0). \quad (11)$$

For the sake of completeness, the main processing steps of eIpDFT algorithm are briefly summarized. Given a data window of N_{dft} samples, the signal DFT is computed with a fixed resolution of $F_{\text{dft}} = f_s/N_{\text{dft}}$. A peak search routine identifies the DFT maximum, whose bin index k_0 is used to provide a first approximation of the fundamental frequency normalized by F_{dft} . In such (quasi-)sinusoidal conditions, it is reasonable to assume that the true signal frequency differs from its finite approximation by a fractional term δ_{dft} that is limited within $\pm F_{\text{dft}}/2$. By interpolating a sinc function on the DFT bins surrounding k_0 , it is possible to identify δ_{dft} and thus provide a corrected estimation of the fundamental frequency, amplitude, and initial phase. Based on these estimates, it is also possible to simulate the long-range spectral leakage coming from the negative image component and minimize its interference in the final estimates.

However, e-IPDFT relies on the assumption that the sampling rate is uniform and perfectly known *a priori*. In practice, though, a perfectly synchronous sampling is not feasible. In particular, if the actual sampling rate \tilde{f}_s differs from its nominal value f_s , a further correction term is needed. Indeed, in a DFT calculation, a sampling rate discrepancy δf_s

corresponds to the variation in the signal frequency that can be well-approximated by a first-order Taylor series expansion

$$\tilde{f}_{\text{sig}} \approx f_{\text{sig}} \cdot \frac{\tilde{f}_s}{f_s} = f_{\text{sig}} \cdot \frac{f_s \pm \delta f_s}{f_s} \quad (12)$$

where the sign of δf_s depends on which module operates at the nonnominal sampling rate. More precisely, positive and negative signs correspond to an incorrect sampling rate of DAC and ADC, respectively.

In the presence of nonideal sampling conditions, the DFT peak and its surrounding bins might be shifted and altered. Therefore, also the frequency provided by the interpolation procedure might not coincide with the actual signal frequency

$$f_0 \neq f_{\text{sig}} \quad (13)$$

and the initial phase also has to be suitably

$$\phi_{\text{sig}} = \phi_0 - \delta k \cdot \frac{N_{\text{dft}} - 1}{N_{\text{dft}}} \pi \quad (14)$$

where δk accounts for the overall fractional bin offset due to both violated assumptions, that is, nonsynchronous sampling and sampling rate not known exactly *a priori*

$$\delta k = \tilde{f}_{\text{sig}} \cdot \frac{N_{\text{dft}}}{f_s} - k_0 = \frac{N_{\text{dft}}}{f_s} \cdot (\tilde{f}_{\text{sig}} - f_{\text{sig}}). \quad (15)$$

Equation (14) can be obtained from the Fourier series of a single-tone sinusoidal by applying the geometric summation formula. Since we consider relative long time windows (i.e., 4 s), the effect of the harmonics in the determination of the corrected phase can be neglected [25]. For this reason, in this article, (14) is used to eventually correct both the WRS and PRS phases. By substituting (15) in (12), the fractional bin offset can be expressed as a function of the sampling rate discrepancy δf_s

$$\delta k = f_{\text{sig}} \cdot \frac{N_{\text{dft}}}{f_s} \cdot \left(\frac{f_s \pm \delta f_s}{f_s} - 1 \right). \quad (16)$$

In the considered calibration system, the sampling rate discrepancy is derived directly from the NI PXI 4461 boards that provide the coerced sampling rate used in both generation and acquisition processes. To verify the reliability of this information, the correctness of the coerced ADC sampling rate has been verified by means of the sine fitting method of IEEE Std 1241 [27].

It is worth noticing that (15) also accounts for the case where the combination of f_s and f_{wrs} does not provide any N_{dft} corresponding to an integer number of cycles. This simplified interpolation method allows for reducing the estimation error at the expense of a computational complexity that is compatible with an on-line analysis. Indeed, the proposed method can be run in parallel with the calibration process and can provide on-line correction factors for the definition of the ground-truth values of signal frequency and initial phase.

C. Estimation Error and Uncertainty

The accuracy of ϕ_{DAC} estimation mainly depends on the fractional bin offset δk causing improper synchronization

Fig. 4. Phase offset estimation error ε as a function of the fractional bin offset δk in log-log scale for the noiseless, 85-dB, and 65-dB scenario in black, red, and blue, respectively. The lines indicate the mean errors, whereas the shaded areas represent the corresponding standard deviations.

between PRS and WRS due to trigger latency and sampling rate discrepancies. In this context, extensive numerical simulations have been carried out to determine the algorithm performance as a function of the operating conditions (e.g., noise level, sampling rate) in terms of phase error

$$\varepsilon = \phi_{\text{DAC}} - \hat{\phi}_{\text{DAC}} \quad (17)$$

where ϕ_{DAC} is the proposed method estimate and $\hat{\phi}_{\text{DAC}}$ is the user-defined phase offset applied to the WRS.

For this analysis, we set the PRS and WRS frequency equal to 20 and 60 Hz, respectively, whereas both ADC and DAC adopt a sampling rate of 153.6 kSa/s, in compliance with the IEC Std requirements. The DFT window lasts 4 s. The measurement noise inherent in the acquisition process has been modeled as purely additive and uncorrelated white Gaussian noise. Then, we modified the WRS frequency to reproduce a fractional bin offset δk within the range $[-0.5, 0.5]$. As expected, the estimation errors show a symmetric trend, centered around $\delta k = 0$. In this regard, Fig. 4 presents the estimation error as a function of the fractional bin offset with three different noise levels. In particular, we considered the ideal noiseless case, and two realistic operating conditions, namely, signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) equal to 85 and 65 dB. The first case accounts for the estimation errors due to the mathematical approximations in (12), whereas the other two correspond to an equivalent number of 13 and 10 bits, respectively. The first contribution is deterministic, whereas the other two are expressed in terms of error mean (lines) and standard deviations (shaded areas) as computed over 100 independent noise realizations. In the noiseless case, the error decreases exponentially with δk , guaranteeing an accuracy level that is function of the DFT frequency resolution [26]. The addition of the white Gaussian noise, instead, produces an error saturation that depends on the SNR level.

Fig. 5. Phase offset estimation error ε as a function of the number of samples per cycle in log-log scale for the noiseless, 85-dB, and 65-dB scenario in black, red, and blue, respectively. The lines indicate the mean errors, whereas the shaded areas represent the corresponding standard deviations.

The error saturation also depends on the number of samples per cycle. Indeed, given a SNR level, a higher number of samples, that is, a finer DFT resolution, corresponds to a lower noise base-level in the DFT bins and thus a lower interference in the definition of ϕ_0 . In Fig. 5 we present the estimation error as a function of the ratio f_s/f_{wrs} for the three aforementioned configurations: noiseless, 85 dB, and 65 dB. For this analysis, the deviation between \tilde{f}_{wrs} and the nominal frequency f_{wrs} has been set equal to 1 ppm. In the noiseless case, the estimation error is constant for any number of samples per cycle larger than 100. Below that threshold, the DFT frequency resolution is too poor and the estimation error rapidly increases with exponential trend. A similar behavior can be observed in the presence of additive noise: the lower the SNR, the higher the minimum number of samples per cycle to guarantee an optimal estimation error. The uncertainty on the phase determination due to the noise has been quantified, also by means of numerical simulations, for signals with a number of samples per cycle larger than 10^4 . The trend of the uncertainty as a function of the SNR is exponential and slightly differs between WRS and PRS. The uncertainty values ranges from 750 ns for a SNR of 65 dB to 80 ns for a SNR of 85 dB.

By properly setting the acquisition parameters, it is possible to keep the estimation error in the order of $3.5 \mu\text{rad}$ with a standard deviation dependent on the noise level, typically oscillating within 0.6 and $3 \mu\text{rad}$ for 85 and 65 dB, respectively. Evidently, even higher accuracy levels can be achieved at the expense of more sophisticated techniques and more computationally demanding methods. Nevertheless, such performance is compliant with the requirements of an IEC Std calibration unit and can be run in parallel with the compliance tests on the DUT (the only additional task is represented by the acquisition and processing of the PRS).

The characterization of the proposed method is concluded by an evaluation of the main uncertainty sources in the

considered measurement setup. A rigorous uncertainty budget is beyond the scope of this article. Nevertheless, a preliminary analysis of the most challenging technological aspects will help in identifying the possible development of the proposed method and the calibrator architecture.

The NI PXI 4461 adopts the same sampling rate for both generation and acquisition tasks. As a consequence, we assume that the estimation of the WRS initial phase is not affected by possible sampling rate discrepancies, that is, $\tilde{f}_s \neq f_s$. The same does not hold for the PRS, which is a logic signal output by the NI PXI 6683, locked to the internal time-base. For this reason, a nonsynchronous sampling might affect the phase estimation and, thus, the compensation of the ADC contribution. In this regard, it is important to also consider the different nature of PRS and WRS signals, as correctly pointed out in [17]. The filtering response of the ADC analog front-end might differ based on the spectral characteristics of the input signal: PRS is a square wave with continuous spectrum, whereas WRS is a sinusoid whose frequency lies well below the Nyquist rate. Nevertheless, NI PXI 4461 is equipped with an optimized digital anti-aliasing filter: in the considered ranges for both f_s and f_{prs} , the recorded DFT preserves up to 2047 odd harmonics of the fundamental frequency. As a consequence, the distortion introduced in the estimation of the PRS phase offset is in the order of 0.01 nrad, which can be neglected in the considered application scenario.

In the considered calibration system, the choice of DAC and ADC sampling rate descends directly from the SV sampling rates, that is, 80 or 256 Sa/cycle at nominal system frequency of 50 or 60 Hz, as provided by the IEC 61850-9-2 implementation guidelines [28]. As a consequence, the nominal sampling rate for 50- and 60-Hz signals is set equal to 192 kSa/s and 153.6 kSa/s, respectively. In both cases, the discrepancy between nominal and coerced sampling rate is in the order of few tens of $\mu\text{Sa/s}$ and does not exceed 1 ppb

$$\begin{aligned} f_s &= 192.0 \text{ kSa/s}, & \delta f_s &\approx 60 \text{ } \mu\text{Sa/s} \approx 0.3 \text{ ppb} \\ f_s &= 153.6 \text{ kSa/s}, & \delta f_s &\approx 0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{Sa/s} \approx 1 \text{ ppb}. \end{aligned}$$

IV. VALIDATION

In this section, the proposed method is validated against two reference methods: one based on an oscilloscope comparison and a nonlinear fitting routine.

A. Oscilloscope Comparison

The first validation method consists of a phase comparison on a high-resolution oscilloscope. In more detail, the oscilloscope receives three inputs: the PPS from the GPS reference clock, the PRS from the time and synchronization module, and the WRS from the DAC. The PPS serves as trigger and guarantees traceability up to the common time reference. By means of high-resolution cursors, it is possible to accurately measure the delay of the PRS and WRS rising edges, namely, t_{prs} and t_{wrs} , with respect to PPS occurrence. Then, a simple subtraction yields the DAC time delay, that is, $t_{\text{DAC}} = t_{\text{wrs}} - t_{\text{prs}}$.

Fig. 6. DAC delays as measured by the proposed method (circles) and the validation method (triangles). The vertical bars represent the uncertainty of the fast current comparator. The WRS frequency is set equal to 10 kHz (top). The estimate difference corresponds to the systematic contribution of the fast current comparator (bottom).

In the considered frequency range, the oscilloscope might struggle in detecting the zero-crossing of a sinusoidal waveform in an accurate and stable way. Accordingly, the WRS is previously rectified by means of a fast current comparator. Such a device has been designed *ad hoc* in the METAS workshops and its frequency response has been rigorously characterized by means of extensive laboratory tests. Using reference calibration sources, we quantified the comparator delay in the slow rate range of interest (from 1 to 250 kV/s) in terms of mean and standard deviation. The first term represents a systematic error and can be compensated, whereas the second term accounts for the uncertainty of the rectifier circuitry. The delay introduced by the comparator t_{cmp} has been characterized as a function of the signal slew rate S_{cmp} and can be described as follows:

$$\log(t_{\text{cmp}}) = (-0.9 \pm 0.1) \cdot \log(S_{\text{cmp}}) + (8.5 \pm 0.3). \quad (18)$$

In a logarithmic scale, the linear dependency of t_{cmp} on S_{cmp} is visible up to slew rates of $6 \cdot 10^4$ V/s. For higher values of S_{cmp} , the comparator always introduces the same delay of about 75 ns. Based on this preliminary characterization, the comparator proved to guarantee an uncertainty from 270 to 6 ns in the range between 1 and 50 kHz. As a consequence, we carried out several validation tests where the WRS signal, updated with different rates, is generated with frequency values ranging from 1 to 10 kHz. The amplitude range allowed by the DAC board has been entirely tested. According to the specifications of the NI PXI 4461 module, the worst case discrepancy in the actual sampling rate $\delta f_s / f_s$ does not exceed 1 ppb for the sampling rates tested.

In this context, Fig. 6 illustrates, as an example, the t_{DAC} estimate as provided by the described validation method, using a WRS with frequency $f_{\text{wrs}} = 10$ kHz and 4-V amplitude (i.e., a slew rate of 40 kV/s) updated with a rate of 200 kSa/s. To assess the repeatability of the obtained results, each test is

repeated ten times. The DAC delay range is attributable to the update rate adopted, whereas the difference in values (of a few tens of ns) between the repeated tests is due to the nonrepeatability of the hardware. Nevertheless, it is interesting to observe the consistency of both methods' estimates. As shown by the bottom graph, the estimate differences are nearly constant, where the line and shaded area represent the mean values and standard deviations, respectively. The estimates of the validation method tend to exceed the proposed method one by nearly 185 ns. This is totally consistent with the delay introduced by the current comparator of $(178 \pm 84 \text{ ns})$ as calculated with (18).

B. Nonlinear Fit

The second reference method consists of a nonlinear fitting routine for accurate definition of digitizers' absolute phase. The PRS and WRS records are fit against two mathematical models that account for the low-pass filtering stage inherent in the ADC front-end and determine the time delay with respect to a common time reference, that is, the PPS that triggers the generation and reacquisition process. In particular, the WRS is fit against a sinusoidal model that also accounts for the possible presence of additive dc offsets, whereas the PRS model is intended to replicate the low-pass filtering effect of the analog front-end of the ADC board. A more detailed description of the nonlinear fit method and the rigorous characterization of its estimation uncertainty go beyond the scope of this article and are available in [19].

It is worth noticing that this method entirely relies on the mathematical models for PRS and WRS, whose correspondence with the actual experimental data might influence significantly the fit results. Differently from the proposed method, this implies a detailed preliminary analysis: particularly in the PRS case, the adoption of oversampling techniques, like the equivalent time sampling (ETS), is envisioned to suitably identify the model of such rapid edges.

In the considered setup, the WRS can be reliably approximated by a purely sinusoidal model

$$x_{\text{wrs}}(t) = a \cdot \sin(2\pi b \cdot (t + c)) + d \quad (19)$$

where a , b , and c represent the sine amplitude, frequency, and time delay, respectively, and d accounts for a possible dc offset, whereas t is the independent time variable. The PRS model, instead, approximates the low-pass filtered version of a square-wave rising edge as a customized logistic or sigmoid function

$$x_{\text{prs}}(t) = a \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-b \cdot (t-c)}} + d \quad (20)$$

where a , b , and c determine the amplitude, slew rate, and time delay of the sigmoid, respectively, and d is the dc offset.

In both models (19) and (20), the c parameter coincides with the desired time delay, namely, t_{wrs} and t_{prs} . Then, t_{dac} descends immediately as their difference and is converted into the corresponding phase offset based on f_{wrs} .

The nonlinear fit routine, though, relies on an iterative optimization algorithm, the well-known Levenberg-Marquardt method, whose convergence to the global optimum depends on

Fig. 7. Comparison of PRS rising edge as a function of sampling rate: 153.6 kSa/s in red and 192 kSa/s in blue. PRS frequency is equal to 50 Hz.

the parameter initial guesses. In this regard, it is reasonable to say that in the considered calibration scenario, the user has a nearly complete control on the generation of both waveforms (e.g., user-defined frequency or time delay) and a detailed knowledge of systematic feature (e.g., full-scale amplitude of the sinusoidal signal, high- and low-level amplitude of the TTL signal). As a consequence, the initial guesses are expected to lie in a restricted neighborhood of the actual values [7].

For this validation analysis, we consider four different configurations, where we vary the WRS and PRS frequency between 50 and 60 Hz, and the sampling rate between 153.6 and 192 kSa/s, respectively. By applying the ETS technique, we are able to shift the sampling occurrence with respect to the digitizer clock by integer multiples of 200 ns, corresponding to an “equivalent” sampling rate of 5 MSa/s.

In this regard, Fig. 7 compares the ETS acquisition of the rising edge of a PRS at 50 Hz. At 153.6 kSa/s, the filtering effect is more significant, producing a longer rise time and smoother transitions. Conversely, at 192 kSa/s the analog front-end presents a larger passbandwidth, resulting in a shorter rise time, and also in a higher oscillations. Similar considerations may be applied also to the WRS, but the sinusoidal function is characterized by a much lower slew rate at the frequencies under investigation, that is, 50 and 60 Hz.

Based on these considerations, the nonlinear fit has to be initialized accordingly. For the sake of clarity, Table I reports the initial guesses for both models' parameters as a function of sampling rate. The final row provides the mean μ_{GOF} and standard deviation σ_{GOF} of the goodness of fit (GOF), as computed over 25 independent experiments. For this analysis, we select the coefficient of determination R^2 as GOF metric, since it quantifies the statistical correlation between the fit model and the acquired dataset. In this regard, it is worth noticing that all the considered configurations guarantee an excellent matching with the acquired data, as proven by the GOF index values not lower than 98%.

In Table II, we report the fit estimates of ϕ_{DAC} : for each configuration, we provide the mean and standard deviation as

TABLE I
NONLINEAR FIT-INITIAL GUESSES

	WRS MODEL (19)		PRS MODEL (20)	
	153.6 kSa/s	192 kSa/s	153.6 kHz	192 kSa/s
a	8	8	4.60	4.33
b	50 (60)	50 (60)	$4.5 \cdot 10^5$	$6.4 \cdot 10^5$
c	0	0	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$
d	0	0	-0.66	-0.48
μ_{GOF} [%]	99.9	99.9	98.3	99.4
σ_{GOF} [%]	0.1	0.1	1.2	0.4

TABLE II
NONLINEAR FIT VALIDATION RESULTS VERSUS PROPOSED METHOD

Method	f_s [kSa/s]	ϕ_{DAC} [mrad]	
		mean	std. dev.
proposed	153.6	7.864	0.004
	192	4.186	0.004
non-linear fit	153.6	7.944	0.003
	192	4.195	0.003

computed over 50 or 60 independent repetitions, depending on the adopted PRS frequency. It is worth noticing how the fit results confirm the proposed method results and confirm the systematic delay inherent in the specific generation and reacquisition measurement chain. The difference between ϕ_{DAC} determined with the proposed and the nonlinear fit method is $80 \mu\text{rad}$ for $f_s = 153.6 \text{ kSa/s}$ and $9 \mu\text{rad}$ for $f_s = 192 \text{ kSa/s}$. Both methods present comparable standard deviations of 4 and $3 \mu\text{rad}$, respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

In this article, we present a novel method for accurate and fast estimation of the DAC phase offset in IEC Std 61850-9-2 calibration systems, but easy to customize to other application scenarios.

The presented method relies on a combined DFT analysis of the PRS and WRS signals. The first one is locked to the system time-base and guarantees the traceability up to UTC. The second one accounts for the phase offset contributions introduced in the measurement chain consisting of generation and reacquisition. By means of extensive numerical simulations, we characterize the estimation accuracy in the expected operating conditions, as well as its dependency from measurement noise and incorrect sampling rate. In average operational condition, 1-ppm uncertainty on the frequency with 85-dB SNR signal, this error has been estimated to be $3.5 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{rad}$.

The method has been validated against two different reference techniques. The first one, which consists in comparing PRS and WRS (rectified through a fast current comparator) at the oscilloscope, shows empirically that the difference between the measured and computed DAC delay (in time domain) remains constant at 185 ns. This difference is consistent with the delay introduced by the fast current comparator for the measured WRS' slew rate. The second approach, which

consists in determining the phase offset through a nonlinear fitting routine performed on the resampled reacquired signals, confirms the systematic phase offsets due to the DAC generation chain. In this case, the differences between the results of the presented and the validation method are within $80 \mu\text{rad}$ with comparable standard deviations of $4 \mu\text{rad}$.

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